

WP4 Review and identification of innovative economic and financial instruments

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1. Background and objectives of this document

Govaqua's main objective is to facilitate a transition towards sustainable and equitable water use in Europe. This involves identifying, assessing, and validating innovative governance instruments and approaches. The urgency stems from the need to reconcile water use with environmental needs and align with EU directives and global sustainability goals.

Govaqua employs an interdisciplinary methodology, analyzing existing water governance systems across Europe, with a focus on various sectors such as agriculture, industries, energy, and citizen involvement. A key innovation is the conceptualization of sustainability transition in water governance, with established criteria and indicators for assessment.

Addressing systemic development needs, the project covers governance innovations in legislation, multi-stakeholder participation, economics, finance, and digital solutions. Good practices in these areas are reviewed, analyzed, and co-developed in real-world situations across Living Labs in different European locations.

Despite significant scientific advancements, a notable dearth of empirical evidence persists regarding the optimal timing, types, and contextual appropriateness of economic instruments. Within the context of water scarcity, degradation of water quality, disruption to ecosystems, and the associated risk of supply failure, it is deemed imperative to initiate research endeavors aimed at identifying, evaluating, developing, and validating innovative governance instruments and approaches. The primary objective of the Govaqua Work Package 4 (WP4) is to furnish policy recommendations for the incorporation of economic and financial instruments into EU water policies and governance schemes, by:

- Identifying and analysing innovative economic and financial instruments from an economic, political and social perspective and developing an analytical framework for the assessment of their economic performance.
- Perform an in-depth analysis of governance approaches and concepts (investments, risk management, water pricing, cost-benefits) that relate to economic and financial instruments, through case studies and Living Labs, assessing the role of these instruments in governance in the water sector.

This document, which is embedded in the primary objective of facilitating the transition towards sustainable and equitable water use in Europe, aims to provide a comprehensive review of innovative economic and financial instruments (EFIs). In order to achieve this, a taxonomy of such instruments is developed and an analytical framework for their assessment is offered.

The governance of water resources presents a multifaceted challenge that necessitates a holistic approach, integrating legal, regulatory, and economic tools. This is addressed in various Govaqua work packages aimed at ensuring sustainable management. Economic and financial instruments (EFIs) have emerged as a promising solution to water-related challenges, offering a means of achieving a balance between economic efficiency and environmental sustainability (Lago et al., 2015). EFIs can facilitate the optimal allocation of water, promote conservation, and reflect its true cost. Nevertheless, the efficacy of these instruments is contingent upon their meticulous

design and implementation, in addition to consideration of the extant legal and regulatory context (OECD, 2015).

The development of Deliverable D4.1 builds on and is interlinked with the fundamental elements established in other work packages:

- A key input of WP2 is the definition of water rights, be they quantitative volumetric rights or qualitative requirements related to water quality. These definitions are prerequisites for the application of economic instruments such as the polluter pays principle, water charges, water trading mechanisms, tariffs and taxes. Without a clear legal and institutional framework, the application of these tools would lack legitimacy and effectiveness.
- Social considerations, on which WP3 focuses, also play a vital role in issues such as the acceptability of water trading, stakeholder participation, voluntary agreements, etc.
- Finally, the broader objectives and targets outlined in WP1 provide overall guidance for D4.1. By aligning with the project's vision for sustainable transition in water governance, the outcome integrates background research, practical applications and strategic recommendations.

Deliverable D4.1 also plays a key role in supporting multiple thematic work packages (WP) within the GOVAQUA project.

- Its main contribution to WP1 is to provide basic information on EFIs that promote sustainable water use. This deliverable directly supports the development and testing of the D1.3 water governance assessment tool, assisting in the formulation of general recommendations for the transition towards sustainable water governance.
- In WP6, D4.1 contributes to the establishment of Living Labs by providing a detailed review of EFIs, complemented by case studies and their implementation in various contexts. This information forms the basis for the design of Living Labs tailored to specific governance challenges, fostering a practical approach to the application of economic and financial tools in water management.
- For WP7, the deliverable serves as a key resource for the development of policy briefs. These reports are intended to inform policy makers, river basin managers and stakeholders in the water use sectors.

In addition, a selection of case studies associated with different Economic and Financing Instruments is also provided in this document, which will serve as a basis for the next phase of work, where case studies will be selected for analysis.

Figure 1. Positioning of the analysis of thematic water governance innovations in WP4 the economic and financial instruments, and this deliverable in the overall framework of the GOVAQUA project.

The document is structured as follows: the next section “The role of taxonomies of economic instruments on environmental policy” explores the goals and significance of taxonomies in shaping environmental policy. Section 3 presents a practical summary table of EFIs accompanied by case studies. This section aims to offer a concise overview and practical insights into the application of different EFIs. Section 4 delves into the mechanical aspects of the dynamic effects generated by economic instruments. Section 5 introduces a simple yet comprehensive framework for assessing economic instruments in the context of case studies. Finally, section 6 summarizes key findings, and insights of this document.

2. The role of taxonomies of economic instruments on environmental policy

In the field of economics, “taxonomy” refers to the systematic categorization and classification of economic concepts, models, and theories into distinct groups based on their similarities and differences. Taxonomy plays an important role in economic research, education, and policymaking by providing a structured framework for understanding and organizing complex economic concepts and phenomena (Samuelson and Nordhaus 2009)

The goal of taxonomy is to create a clear and consistent general framework that can be used for understanding and analysing a particular subject or domain. However, it's noteworthy that in the specific context of economic instruments for water governance, there is currently no established taxonomy. This absence poses a challenge in providing a systematic categorisation and analysis

of these instruments, as the taxonomy provides a structured way to categorise and analyse different types of instruments based on their theoretical principles and underlying characteristics. This allows policymakers and researchers to better understand the strengths and weaknesses of different policy instruments and to make more informed decisions about which instruments to use in different contexts.

An example of use of taxonomy in economic field is the European Investment Bank (EIB) taxonomy is known as the "EIB Environmental, Social and Governance (Perni et al.) Policy Framework" ¹ and was developed to support the implementation of the European Union's sustainable finance agenda to classify its investments and lending activities according to their environmental sustainability criteria.

Concerning environmental governance, the OECD (OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) 2009) differentiates between incentive-based instruments and command-and-control instruments, aligning with the majority of scholarly perspectives (e.g.,(Fullerton 2001; Goulder and Parry 2008; Gupta et al. 2007; Whitten et al. 2003), being this a very common way to consider the range of environmental policy instruments.

All forms of Economic and financial Instruments (EFIs) necessitate administrative participation, however the level of government intervention may differ across instruments. Notably, there has been growing interest in low-intervention tools, including developmental strategies, voluntary measures (Gupta et al. 2007); OECD (OECD) (2009) and market-friction reductions (Revesz and Stavins 2004; Whitten et al. 2003) among others. By summarizing the information from these studies, the authors can identify patterns and trends in the use of environmental policy instruments, which can inform the development of a taxonomy, which will be developed in the next section.

3. A taxonomic analysis of economic and financing ²instruments in water

The analysis of environmental policy instruments underscores the imperative to incorporate explicit dimensions for the systematic organization and characterization of these instruments. In general terms, it can be asserted that environmental policy measures aim to instigate alterations or discourage prevailing behaviors. The dynamic aspect of the resultant behavioral changes warrants consideration, including the incorporation of self-enforcing measures as opposed to other static marginal adjustments. Pannell (Pannell) mention this change goals within the context of a study assessing the levels of public and private net benefits they engender. Regrettably, this perspective has not received widespread attention.

¹ European Commission (2020a) Regulation (EU) 2020/852 (Taxonomy) on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, see <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32020R0852>

² From now on referred to just as economic instruments

In this vein, the authors advocate for the inclusion of two discerning dimensions that play pivotal roles in understanding the dynamics of these instruments: the power to introduce transaction and the type of change induced.

- Power to Introduce Transaction. The first proposed dimension, the power to introduce transaction, delves into the institutional and procedural aspects of environmental policy implementation. This dimension seeks to elucidate the authority and influence wielded by various stakeholders in the introduction and execution of policy transactions
- Type of Change Induced (Marginal or Radical). The second dimension posited by the authors revolves around the nature of change instigated by environmental policy instruments. Specifically, it distinguishes between marginal and radical changes. Marginal changes denote incremental adjustments or modifications within existing frameworks, while radical changes signify transformative shifts that alter fundamental aspects of environmental governance. This dimension provides a critical lens through which to assess the transformative potential of policy instruments, addressing whether they merely tweak existing structures or instigate paradigmatic shifts in environmental policy. By categorizing the type of change induced, policymakers and researchers can better grasp the overall impact and efficacy of different environmental policy instruments.

This will be developed further in section 4.

By introducing these explicit dimensions, it will be possible to create a more nuanced and comprehensive taxonomy of environmental policy instruments. Moreover, this taxonomy can contribute to the development of a more sophisticated understanding of the strategic considerations and implications associated with the implementation of environmental policies. This, in turn, can inform the design and refinement of policies to align more effectively with overarching environmental goals and sustainability objectives.

Table 1 shows a practical approach to water EFIs with a focus on case studies and success/failure analysis. This taxonomy is illustrated by case studies relevant to water practitioners.

Table 1 Economic instruments in water policy

	Economic instruments	Example	References
1	Price-based		
1.1	Abstraction charges	Based on season: England and Wales	Rey et al. (2019)
1.1.1.	Flat rate	Licensing, fixed rate	Molle and Closas (2020b)
1.1.2	Volumetric rate (Increasing Blocks Tariffs', 'Budget pricing', 'Seasonal pricing' etc)	Binomial or volumetric billing	Pronti and Berbel (2023)
1.1.3	Tax	Tax and tariffs water abstraction The Danish Pesticide Tax	Berbel et al. (2019a) Böcker and Finger (2016)
1.2	Emissions charges	Wastewater effluent tax	Möller-Gulland et al. (2015)
1.3	Non-compliance fees	Compliance fees	Loch et al. (2020)
2	Subsidy/subsidy removal		
2.1	Subsidy to capital	Subsidies to water efficiency (AUS, ESP, USA)	Berbel et al(2019b)
2.2	Subsidy to exploitation/ removal	EU-CAP ecoschemes, Environmental Quality Incentives Program (EQIP),	https://www.epa.gov/agriculture ; https://ec.europa.eu/info/food-farming-fisheries/key-policies/common-agricultural-policy_en .
2.3	P.E.S.	Vittel, New York Catskill,	Zanella, Schleyer, and Speelman (2014)
3	Trading schemes		
3.1	Tradable Rights (Water trade)	Bulletin board market (NCWCD in Colorado), clearinghouse and Sealed bid double auctions Water markets: Australia, SW-USA and Spain Option contract: Spain, SW-USA	Hadjigeorgalis (2009) Pujol et al. (2006), Qureshi et al. (2011) Rey et al. (2016)
3.2	Water banks	SW-USA: California, Drought Emergency Water Bank in 1991, Idaho, Montana, Colorado, Texas, Oregon, <Washington Water Trust (NGO)> Spain: Water exchange centre: Guadiana River Basin	Montilla-López et al. (2016), Dellapenna (2001), Clifford et al. (2004)
3.3	Water banking	USA Arizona, Idaho	Megdal et al. (2014); Ghosh, Cobourn, and Elbakidze (2014)
3.4	Buyback	Australia: Murray-Darling Basin SW-USA Spain: Segura, Júcar and Guadiana	Pérez-Blanco and Gutiérrez-Martín (2017), Montilla-López et al. (2016), Palomo-Hierro et al. (2016)
3.5	Credit schemes	Water Benefit Certificate	Tabaichount et al. (2019); Rinaudo et al. 2016; Kieser & McCarthy, 2015

3.6	Tradable emission permit	Water Quality Trading Urban Stormwater Credit Trade	https://epa.ohio.gov/divisions-and-offices/surface-water/reports-data/water-quality-trading-program https://tapin.waternow.org/resources/philadelphia-water-department-stormwater-credit-explorer/
4	Information policies (Value Chain)		
4.1	Product certification schemes	WaterSense label (USA); Blue Angel (Germany)	https://www.epa.gov/watersense ; https://www.blauer-engel.de/en
4.2	Benchmarking	Benchmarking irrigation water use / Urban use	Chabe-Ferret et al. (2019); Lu et al. (2019)
4.3	Water stewardship certifications	Alliance for Water Stewardship International Water Stewardship Standard	https://a4ws.org/
5	Voluntary actions		
5.1	Sector agreement	Data centres water	https://www.datacenterdynamics.com/en/news/european-operators-plan-to-cut-water-use-to-400ml-per-kwh-by-2040/
6	Common Property Resources		
6.1	OUGC, CUAS, Nebraska Nature	OUGC(FR), CUAS (ES), Nebraska NCD (USA)	Adelman and Taylor (2003) Rouillard et al. (2021)
7	Impact investments		
7.1	Environmental Impact bonds	Finnish Cases on water governance and agriculture, USA	Tiikkainen et al. (2022), Balboa (2016) Landers (2016), Herrera et al. (2019), Brand et al. (2021), O'Flynn et al (2022), Brand et al (2020).
7.2	Private equity impact funds	S-Bank regenerative agriculture	https://www.s-pankki.fi/uudistava-maatalous ; De Amicis et al. (2020)

3.1 Price-based

Pricing mechanisms in the context of water governance can be defined as the strategic utilization of fees and tariffs with the dual purpose of generating revenues and influencing specific decision-making behaviors among water users (Finney 2013)

3.1.1 Abstraction charges are fees charged by authority or private supplier for use of conventional (surface and groundwater (GW)) or non-conventional (reclaimed wastewater (WW), desalinated water). Water abstraction charges may be collected on a flat rate (e.g., per hectare) or volumetric system, or mixed (two-part system) approach. Water charges may be reflecting the full cost recovery of maintaining water services and status or may also include a tax that reflects (partly) the externalities or the resource rent for agents (Finney 2013)

3.1.2 Emissions charges, a wastewater effluent tax or a discharge fee, is levied by authorities intended to discourage pollution. Such measure, typically involve charging a fee based on the volume and concentration of pollutants. The revenue generated from wastewater effluent taxes is often used to fund water pollution reduction investments (Möller-Gulland et al. 2015).

3.1.3 Non-compliance fees, are charges imposed on water users who fail to comply with regulations related to water abstraction or discharge activities. These fees are penalties intended to discourage non-compliance and to compensate for the negative impacts (Loch et al. 2020).

3.2 Subsidy/subsidy removal

Financial support mechanisms provided to various water-related activities or practices, aimed at influencing user behaviour, promoting the modernisation of systems or methods used and the conservation of water bodies, among others.

3.2.1 Subsidies to water conservation, either to capital (investment) or to exploitation, they are present in the urban sector (e.g., rebates on water-efficient appliances, landscape conversion, etc.) and the agricultural sector (e.g., irrigation efficiency upgrade and conveyance losses reduction). There is some evidence of rebound effect (higher consumption as a response to higher water use efficiency) in urban and agrarian sector, especially in the later. Rebound effect can be avoided with proper policy measures including water pricing volumetric (Berbel and Mateos 2014).

3.2.2 Subsidy application or subsidies removal. In the context of irrigation water refers to the difference between what farmers actually pay for each unit of irrigation water and the full cost price of water. Historically, irrigation water has been heavily subsidized in both developed and developing countries, leading to inefficient water use by farmers. This inefficiency results in environmental problems. Eliminating these subsidies and reinvesting the fiscal savings in efficient water use technologies could improve Water Use Efficiency (WUE) and yield substantial monetary benefits. However, transitioning from current negative subsidies to positive subsidies for improved efficiency poses various challenges (Tiwari and Dinar 2002).

3.2.3 Payment for environmental services (Muradian et al.) is a mechanism that provides financial incentives to individuals or organizations for the conservation and sustainable use of natural resources, including water quantity and quality. Payments for Ecosystem Services (Muradian et al.) have gained popularity in the last two decades as a policy instrument. The appeal of PES lies in its seemingly straightforward rationale, however, despite its apparent simplicity, implementing PES schemes is a complex task as they are the result from intricate ecological interactions, many of which are only moderately understood (Zanella et al. 2014)

3.3 Trading schemes

Refers to structured systems or mechanisms that allow for the purchase and sale of water rights or allocations between interested parties (Pujol et al. 2006). Trading regimes are designed to promote more efficient

management of water resources by allowing the transfer of water rights between users, encouraging flexibility and promoting sustainable water use practices.

3.3.1 Tradable Rights (Water trade) are a range of systems (Delacámara et al. 2015), although the best known in this category is "cap and trade", which consists of setting a limit or "cap" on the total amount of water that can be used in a specific area or basin and allocating this cap to each individual agent (e.g. irrigated farmers, stakeholders, brokers...). This cap would be adjusted each year based on the available resources, and all water allocated within this cap would be marketable so that water rights can be bought and sold in a similar way to other commodities (although there are some technical constraints) (Lago et al. 2015).

3.3.2 Water banks are mechanisms through which an administrative agency acts as an essential intermediary in the trading of rights (Hadjigeorgalis 2009). Some water banks are operated by government agencies, while others are managed by private organizations or individuals.

3.3.3 Water banking is a water management mechanism designed to manage water supply variability. This system is more often related to groundwater (Megdal et al. 2014). Water reserves can be created by using aquifer space or surface reservoir to store water during the years and seasons when there is abundant rainfall or reclaimed wastewater. It can then be pumped and used during years/seasons that have a deficit.

3.3.4 Buyback or reacquisition of water is the purchase of permanent water rights to restore the balance in overexploited basins (Grafton and Wheeler 2018). Reacquisitions are operated through purchase tenders that compensate irrigators who decide to surrender (part of) their right to withdraw water. Government agencies typically set in advance price and budgetary thresholds to control costs to avoid possible price inflation.–The water recovered is then used to benefit the environment and the communities that depend on it.

3.3.5 Water credits refer to a system in which agents can earn credits for conserving water or reducing their water usage. The concept is still relatively new and not widely implemented. These credits can then be sold or traded to other parties who may need additional water resources. The idea behind water credits is to create a market-based approach to water conservation and management by providing financial incentives for reducing water usage. Examples of such incentives encompass the installation of water-efficient technologies or practices, or implementing measures to capture and reuse water. Thus, the aim is to motivate individuals and organizations to take actions to conserve water and reduce wasteful practices. The credits can then be used to offset the cost of purchasing additional water supplies, or they can be sold to other parties who need to meet water usage requirements. (Abu Madi et al. 2008)

3.3.6 Tradable emission permit is a tool for achieving water quality improvement. Under the right circumstances, water quality trading has the potential to yield both environmental and economic benefits. These tools can promote the interaction among watershed stakeholders, there are examples for water quality and urban stormwater management

3.4 Information policies (Value Chain)

The concept of "information policies" in the context of water governance and the value chain is multifaceted, encompassing various strategies aimed at promoting responsible water management practices.

3.4.1 Product certification schemes are designed to promote more responsible water management practices (including diffuse pollution). Criteria may include factors such as water efficiency, water recycling and reuse, the use of sustainable water sources, and the management of water-related risks such as pollution or depletion of water resources. The use of 'water footprint' should be taken with precaution as there are serious criticism regarding the misleading value of the indicator. The complexities inherent in the concept of "water used" underscore the challenges in developing an indicator that is both robust and universally meaningful (Feres et al. 2017; Perry 2014).

3.4.2 Benchmarking are non-price signals to encourage household water conservation such as benchmarking with peers have been used in irrigation and urban water use context with encouraging results. Lately, there

has been significant attention directed towards exploring the effectiveness of benchmarking with peers in stimulating shifts in pro-environmental actions (Croson and Treich 2014). Social comparison have emerged as a potentially cost-efficient method to induce behavioral changes, even if their impacts are somewhat modest, primarily due to their applicability to a large populace at a minimal expense (Chabe-Ferret et al. 2019).

3.4.3 Water stewardship certifications typically refer to sustainable and responsible practices of business. They can be defined as the use of water that is socially and culturally equitable, environmentally sustainable and economically beneficial. They are achieved through a stakeholder-inclusive process that comprises both site- and catchment-based actions (AWS 2023).

3.5 Voluntary actions

Are posited as substitutes for obligatory regulations, suggesting that opting for a voluntary approach may yield more effective environmental protection than relying solely on command and control measures (Heinz 2002). Negotiated among agents, voluntary agreements hinge on genuinely voluntary actions, excluding rewards, penalties, and regulated obligations. These agreements rely on non-monetary incentives, distinct from Payment for Ecosystem Services (Muradian et al.), to encourage agents to take actions or adopt practices that not only benefit them individually but also contribute to addressing water-allocation challenges (Pedersen et al. 2015)

3.6.-Common Property Resources

The conversion of a private owned resources such as water entitlements hold by individual agents to 'common properties' is used in some aquifers as a critical tool to ensure the sustainability of endangered overexploited resource. It could be called co-management, a framework in which responsibilities are jointly assumed by the state (usually represented by government agencies) and the users (often organised in specific entities) (Molle and Closas 2020a). The context of resources overallocation comes from a trajectory where incorrect estimation of resources has determined over-allocation.

3.7 Financing mechanisms

Financing mechanisms cover a variety of methods to mobilize funding for cost-effective water governance. The focus of the review is on impact investments. Impact investments are traditionally defined as financial contributions aimed at generating both measurable social or environmental impacts and financial returns (Clarkin and Cangioni, 2016). However, we propose expanding this definition to encompass donations and payments made without the expectation of direct financial returns. When these contributions fund activities that yield measurable environmental improvements, they effectively serve as investments. These activities not only benefit the broader community but also provide indirect returns to the donor or payer, thus aligning with the core principles of impact investing.

3.7.1 Environmental Impact bonds (EIBs) represent a financial mechanism crafted to raise capital for environmental initiatives. These bonds reimburse both principal and interest by leveraging the financial gains derived from a project's environmental benefits (Brand et al. 2021). Structurally akin to traditional bonds, EIBs involve stakeholders or beneficiaries borrowing the principal with an obligation to repay investors, along with interest, over a specified period. However, a significant departure between EIBs and traditional bonds lies in their repayment model. While traditional bonds are typically repaid from the issuer's general revenues, not necessarily tied to the financing activity, EIBs expressly tie financial performance to the success of the intervention and the revenues and/or cost savings associated with that success (Nicola 2013).

3.7.2 Private equity impact funds are increasingly incorporating environmental, social, and governance (Perni et al.) objectives into their strategies, responding to a surge in public interest in ethical investing. As the demand for fund managers to prioritize environmental and social considerations intensifies, there is a growing

recognition that ESG and impact investing hold the potential to generate robust financial returns. It is acknowledged that it may still be too early to definitively conclude, even though there are encouraging indicators pointing towards the potential alignment of financial performance and positive societal impact (Yang et al. 2019).

4. The dynamic effect of Economic instruments

The static versus dynamic nature of an intervention is not often mentioned in the literature. However, it is critical to understand the effectiveness of the instrument, not only from a short-term perspective but mostly long-term to ensure the sustainability of interventions. This will allow for better decision-making and more effective and sustainable management of water resources.

The concept of static nature in water resources management refers to the ability of an instrument to generate changes without subsequent or spillover effects. In this context, a static intervention, such as implementing a spot water market, can bring about a change in how water resources are allocated without triggering further consequences.

On the other hand, dynamic interventions have side effects that may diminish the effectiveness of the policy and potentially revert the system back to its baseline situation. For instance, the implementation of water tariffs, while aiming to address certain issues, can lead to unintended consequences or side effects that impact the overall efficacy of the policy.

In summary, static interventions cause changes without spillover effects, while dynamic interventions may have unintended consequences that affect the effectiveness of the implemented policy.

Table 2 shows examples of the responses of EFIs. Regarding the type of interventions, we have to distinguish between three types (depending on the duration of the interventions): punctual, discontinuous or continuous.

On the other hand, Figure 2, illustrates various trajectories of policy interventions. These interventions can be broadly categorized into two types: static and dynamic. The term "adaptive response" pertains to how the policies influence the behavior of farmers over time:

- Positive Adaptive Response: Refers to a situation where the farmer's behavior aligns with the desired change intended by the policy. This is beneficial and contributes to the effectiveness of the measure.
- Negative Adaptive Response (Rebound Effect): Describes a scenario where the behavior of farmers diminishes the effectiveness of the policy. For instance, farmers may adjust their practices in a way that counteracts the intended impact of the policy.

In summary, Figure 2 illustrates how different policy trajectories unfold over time. The adaptive responses of farmers, whether positive or negative, influence the effectiveness of static and dynamic interventions. The distinction between short-term and long-term policies (Being short-term policies those to have an effect only for a brief duration, aligning with their temporary nature and long-term policies those to remain in effect for an extended period after implementation) is also highlighted, emphasizing the potential robustness of policies with enduring effects.

Figure 2: Types of trajectories for policy interventions

Source: Own

The importance of trajectories for EFIs has not been explicitly considered. In terms of dynamically adapting to policy instruments, both positive and negative responses, concerning the intended effects of the policy, can be observed. For example, when the goal is abstraction water savings, a continuous intervention such as water price shows a demand elasticity that is higher (less elastic) in the short term than in the long term (Scheierling, Loomis, & Young, 2006), therefore, being a ‘positive dynamic adaptation’, or reinforcing the desired effect of policy. On the contrary, a specific intervention such as water conservation subsidies generates a dynamic response of farmer that tries to capture ‘water savings or return flows’ being the spontaneous rational behavior of farmers that can only be avoided with strict and decisive policy governance.

Table 2: Examples of dynamic effect of Economic Instruments

Response/ Intervention	Static response short term effect	Dynamic adaptation response	Static permanent (robust)
Punctual	n/a	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidy to water conservation (Negative) • R+D, (Positive) • Benchmarking 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Bank (buyback)
Discontinuous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water Bank (leasing) • Subsidies eco-conditional • Subsidy to capital 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-compliance fees (Negative) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sector agreement (environmental education)
Continuous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water pricing (volumetric) ** 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Water rights trade (Negative) • Tradable emission permit (Positive) • Water pricing (volumetric)** 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Common Property Resources: OUGC, CUAS, Nebraska Nature • Product certification schemes

** Elasticity of demand short term is lower than long term

Source: Own elaboration

5. Analytical framework for the assessment of EFIs

Despite the availability of innovative Economic Instruments, it is a fact that governance failures are multiple and affect both developing and industrialized countries, albeit in different ways.

The concept of Water Governance aims to support practical and result-driven public policies based on three interconnected and supportive dimensions of water governance (OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) 2015):

1. **Effectiveness:** This aspect focuses on how governance contributes to establishing clear, sustainable water policy objectives and milestones across all levels of governance. It emphasizes the implementation of these objectives and the attainment of expected targets.
2. **Efficiency:** This facet concentrates on how governance maximizes the advantages of sustainable water management and societal well-being while minimizing costs to society.
3. **Trust and Engagement:** This dimension highlights governance's role in fostering public trust and ensuring the involvement of stakeholders. It emphasizes democratic legitimacy and fairness, striving for inclusivity within society as a whole.
4. **Equity,** instrument should have measures for protection of low income agents. Frequently urban water pricing schemes include a 'social bond' or a special treatment for less favoured collectives.

The assessment of the performance of various Environmental Instruments (Hernández-Pacheco Algaba et al.) in diverse contexts requires careful consideration of a multitude of factors. A successful EFIs should guarantee not only access to water but also the systematic renewal of water services infrastructure, along with a focus on ensuring the quality and restoration of ecosystems. It is crucial to acknowledge that for a tool to function effectively, it must be grounded in and supported by existing legislation and institutions within the specific territory of application. Researchers, in formulating these instruments, often rely on economic assumptions that may not fully capture the intricate institutional constraints present in the complex political reality. Consequently, there is a notable concern among economists about the noticeable gap between the practical implementation of economic instruments and their theoretical representation in economic models (Böcher 2009).

Hence, drawing from the criteria outlined by OECD (2015) for water governance, along with insights from a literature review and the incorporation of dimensions observed in the preceding section, we have formulated a framework. This framework comprises three dimensions, six indicators that the EFIs under evaluation should adhere to varying degrees, and a set of questions linked to each proposed indicator.

5.1 Principles

The principles underpinning this analytical framework will be the building blocks for any successful policy intervention:

1. **Cost-Effectiveness:** Assesses the efficiency and efficacy of interventions concerning the allocation, utilization and maintenance of resources. It focuses on achieving desired outcomes while optimizing resource utilization. In governance, cost-effectiveness analysis helps decision-makers determine the most efficient use of available resources to achieve specific objectives or outcomes. Moreover, The EU Water Framework Directive (WFD) prescribes cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) as an economic tool for the minimisation of costs when formulating programmes of measures to be implemented in the European river basins (European Union 2000).
2. **Political and Participatory Transparency:** This dimension emphasizes the openness, accessibility, and clarity of political processes and decision-making mechanisms. Political transparency involves making information regarding policies, decision-making procedures, and governance structures available and understandable to the public. Participatory transparency goes a step further by ensuring that stakeholders have opportunities to engage, provide input, and participate meaningfully in decision-making processes. Transparency builds trust, enhances accountability, and fosters public confidence in governance systems.

In water governance at the EU level, transparency, viewed through deliberative democracy, is crucial. Deliberative democracy highlights citizen participation beyond voting, emphasizing meaningful engagement in social dialogues (Curtin, 1999) (Curtin, 1999)

Studies show a positive link between citizen participation programs and government transparency (Kim and Lee 2019). This transparency is vital for informed discussions on water governance, economic instruments, water scarcity, and agricultural economics. Emphasizing social dialogue aligns with the interdisciplinary nature of water challenges, involving diverse stakeholders for holistic solutions. Transparency builds trust, enhances accountability, and boosts public confidence in governance.

3. Political and Participatory Feasibility: This dimension assesses the practicality and viability of proposed policies or interventions concerning political and participatory aspects. It involves evaluating whether proposed measures align with the political context, existing regulations, societal values, and stakeholder interests. Feasibility considers not only the technical aspects but also the political will and societal acceptance needed for successful implementation.

Feasibility holds various roles in political theory. While commonly used to eliminate impractical theories, its more valuable role is in ranking alternative theories based on decision-making dimensions. Furthermore, it reveals an agent's powers – if an action is feasible, the agent has the power to undertake it (Lawford-Smith 2012). Therefore, policies must be feasible within the political and social landscape to gain support and implementation.

5.2 Indicators

Building on these principles the seven proposed indicators for assessing the performance of an IE are :

- Impact. Understood as the capacity of the economic instrument to generate significant effects, which may be positive/negative, short/long term, and intended/unintended. This indicator emphasizes the importance of economic instruments in creating substantial effects, including positive impacts on water access, infrastructure renewal, quality, and ecosystem restoration.
- Efficiency: Refers to the optimal allocation of resources to maximize overall societal well-being or the achievement of a specific goal while minimizing waste or inefficiency. Efficiency assesses how well resources are allocated to achieve societal well-being or specific goals, minimizing waste or inefficiency in the process.
- Relevance: understood as the quality of being appropriate or significant in relation to solving water-related problems. This indicator underscores the importance of economic instruments being appropriate and significant in addressing and resolving water-related challenges.
- Coherence: Seen as the instrument's compatibility with other policies of a country, sector, or institution. Coherence assesses whether an economic instrument is compatible with other policies, ensuring a harmonious approach within a country, sector, or institution.
- Effectiveness: Refers to the ability of a policy or instrument to successfully achieve its intended goals and produce the desired outcomes. This indicator evaluates how successful an Economic Instrument is in achieving specific goals, such as water access, infrastructure renewal, and ecosystem restoration.
- Sustainability: Understood as the assurance that the net benefits of the instrument continue or are likely to continue over time. Sustainability focuses on whether the benefits of the economic instrument endure over time, especially considering the systematic renewal of water services infrastructure and ensuring ongoing positive outcomes.
- Equity, provisions for supporting less favoured collectives according affordability or 'disproportionate impact' criteria.

5.3 List of questions

In addition to the indicators, a list of questions that extend the range assessed by the 6 indicators has been developed. It is recognised that a discussion on the performance of an EFI cannot be limited to six indicators and requires reflection on a number of additional questions relating to these indicators. It is important to note that these additional questions are designed to accommodate all the IEs considered, but there are questions that apply to some instruments but not to others. It is up to the evaluator to discuss and answer only the questions related to the EFI being evaluated. Possible answers can be: yes, no, under development or not applicable. In addition, it should be possible to provide sources/references to cross-check the assessment.

- Impact
 - Can the policy instrument generate positive/negative effects? (e.g., the income of some used maybe negatively affected)
 - Can the policy instrument deliver results in the short and long term? (e.g., can the system 'rebound' in the long term to reduce/eliminate the effects of the intended policy?)
 - Are there measures to assess and manage risks?
- Efficiency
 - Are the resources appropriately used?
 - Can the value of water for society be increased compared to current allocation?
 - Is financial cost recovery fully implemented?
 - Are there cross-subsidies between users and society sectors?
 - Is the water pricing-cost recovery well designed? (e.g. implementation of progressive volumetric tariffs)
 - Are there measurable/quantifiable metrics to quantify the impacts of the instrument?
 - Are the investments economically viable to the investors? How long term investments are required? Are the investors committed?
- Relevance
 - Are the instrument well aligned with the objectives and context of the policy?
 - Is the policy addressing a large / small part of the policy goals?
 - Are the stakeholder expectations well known?
 - Is there fragmentation in the sector? Do different stakeholders have different objectives and strategies?
- Coherence
 - Are the instruments integrated?
 - Is the legislative structure fully outlined?
 - Does it allow for the implementation of the legislative structure in the territory? If not, can they be integrated into existing governance systems?
 - Are other policies and regulatory frameworks consistent and allow cost effective impact investments?
 - Is the role of the agents clearly defined by legislation, bylaws, etc? (e.g. public administrations, user associations, public private partnerships, potential investors, outcome providers...)
 - Is the investment understandable? Do investors and other stakeholders understand the complexities and risks?
- Effectiveness

- Are the objectives clearly related to the policy instrument?
- Are the environmental goals achieved under the existing policy framework?
- The selected objective is the most cost-effective for the achievement of policy goals?
- Is the size and liquidity of the market sufficient for the project?
- Sustainability
 - Has the instrument been thoroughly evaluated to understand environmental, social and economic factors as well as the risks?
 - Is there a balance between economic and environmental objectives?
 - Is the transparency and monitoring included in the policy design?
 - Are the results of policy instruments sustainable at long term?
 - Can the policy be flexible for adaptation to change in resources availability (e.g., drought) or societal demands (e.g., changes in policy priorities)
 - Can the policy generate intended/unintended effects?
- Equity
 - Has the instrument been thoroughly evaluated to, social and economic factors for disfavoured collectives?
 - The criteria for economic 'affordability' in low income collectives has been considered?
 - Have the intergenerational impacts been considered, assuming that the costs are borne by the present generation and not passed on to future generations?"
 - Is the territorial and sectoral impact balanced, or, on the contrary, are certain territories or sectors disproportionately affected?

Figure 3 presents a comprehensive overview of the proposed analytical framework, consolidating all principles, indicators, and associated questions into a practical table. This visual representation allows for a clear and organized presentation of the key elements, facilitating a systematic and structured approach to assessing economic instruments in the context of water governance.

<p>POLITICAL AND PARTICIPATORY FEASIBILITY</p> <p>POLITICAL AND PARTICIPATORY TRANSPARENCY</p> <p>COST-EFFECTIVENESS</p>	<p>Impact</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Can the policy instrument generate positive/negative effects? (e.g., the income of some used maybe negatively affected) - Can the policy instrument generate short term/ long term? (e.g., can the system 'rebound' in the long term to reduce/eliminate the effects of the intended policy?) - Are there measures to assess and manage risks?
	<p>Efficiency</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are the resources appropriately used? - Can the value of water for society be increased compared to current allocation? - Is financial cost recovery fully implemented? - Are there cross-subsidies between users and society sectors? - Is the water pricing-cost recovery well designed? (e.g. implementation of progressive volumetric tariffs) - Are there measurable/quantifiable metrics to quantify the impacts of the instrument? - Are the investments economically viable to the investors? How long-term investments are required? Are the investors committed?
	<p>Relevance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are the instruments well aligned with the objectives and context of the policy? - Is the policy addressing a large / small part of the policy goals? - Are the stakeholder expectations well known? - Is there fragmentation in the sector? Do different stakeholders have different objectives and strategies?
	<p>Coherence</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are the instruments integrated? - Is the legislative structure fully outlined? - Does it allow for the implementation of the legislative structure in the territory? If not, can they be integrated into existing governance systems? - Are other policies and regulatory frameworks consistent and allow cost effective impact investments? - Is the role of the agents clearly defined by legislation, bylaws, etc? (e.g. public administrations, user associations, public private partnerships, potential investors, outcome providers...) - Is the investment understandable? Do investors and other stakeholders understand the complexities and risks?
	<p>Effectiveness</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Are the objectives clearly related to the policy instrument? - Are the environmental goals achieved under the existing policy framework? - The selected objective is the most cost-effective for the achievement of policy goals? - Is the size and liquidity of the market sufficient for the project?
	<p>Sustainability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has the instrument been thoroughly evaluated to understand environmental, social and economic factors as well as the risks? - Is there a balance between economic and environmental objectives? - Is the transparency and monitoring included in the policy design? - Are the results of policy instruments sustainable at long term? - Can the policy be flexible for adaptation to change in resources availability (e.g., drought) or societal demands (e.g., changes in policy priorities) - Can the policy generate intended/unintended effects?
	<p>Equity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Has the instrument been thoroughly evaluated to, social and economic factors for disfavoured collectives? - The criteria for economic 'affordability' in low income collectives has been considered? - Have the intergenerational impacts been considered, assuming that the costs are borne by the present generation and not passed on to future generations?" - Is the territorial and sectoral impact balanced, or, on the contrary, are certain territories or sectors disproportionately affected?

Figure 3. Framework for case study analysis

Source: own

6. Concluding remarks

This research has a twofold purpose: a general taxonomy of economic instruments for water environmental policy has been proposed and a comprehensive evaluation framework by a set of principles, indicators and questions with the aim to help policymakers and stakeholders better understand the range of economic instruments available and how they can be applied in different situations.

The taxonomy of economic instruments for environmental policy plays a critical role in promoting effective, evidence-based decision-making and supporting the development and implementation of sustainable environmental policies. Indeed, in the first step, the inclusion of dynamic effects may also give a temporal dimension that focus in long term sustainability and radical or marginal change in the behaviour of agents regarding water resources use.

The different forms that trading schemes can take have been explored in depth, through their market-based approach that allows for an efficient allocation of water resources among different users, to see how they can contribute to promoting sustainable practices, fostering conservation and achieving overall resource management objectives. It is important to note that the effectiveness of trade regimes depends on their design, implementation and the regulatory framework in place. The intricacies of these regimes may vary depending on the specific context and the resource being traded.

Furthermore, the review of financing instruments, with a particular emphasis impact investments, illuminates the strategies for mobilizing funds for efficient water governance. These methods of financing, where the returns or motivations for investment are directly correlated to the tangible, quantifiable results of the investments, lay the groundwork for the effective distribution of funds in water governance.

We conclude that to carry out an in-depth analysis of these EFIs, the framework developed for this purpose provides us with a tool that allows us to systematically assess and analyse these instruments in achieving their intended objectives through a series of principles, indicators and questions. Stakeholders can make informed decisions on their design, modification or possible replacement to better address complex challenges in the areas of water governance, economic sustainability and resource management, and the framework can therefore be used by different stakeholders when assessing different economic instruments.

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